

Potential distribution of the howler monkey (*Alouatta palliata*) in cocoa agrosystems based on a niche model

Baltazar Sanchez Diaz¹, José del Carmen Geronimo Torres², Liliana Ríos Rodas², Azucena del Rosario Fraire Vazquez¹, Rudy Solís Silvan^{1*}

¹Tecnologico Nacional de Mexico. Instituto Tecnológico Superior de Comalcalco. Carretera vecinal, Paraiso - Comalcalco KM², RA Occidente 3ra sección, 86650 Comalcalco, Tabasco, Mexico

²Universidad Autónoma de Chiapas. Facultad maya de Estudios Agropecuarios. Carretera Catazajá - Palenque Km. 4, 29980 Catazajá, Chiapas, Mexico

*Email: rudysolisilvan@gmail.com

Received: 01 August 2022 / Revised: 01 October 2022 / Accepted: 09 October 2022 / Published online: 09 October 2022.

How to cite: Sanchez Diaz, B., Geronimo Torres, J.D.C., Ríos Rodas, L., Fraire Vazquez, A.D.R., Solís Silvan, R. (2023). Potential distribution of the howler monkey (*Alouatta palliata*) in cocoa agrosystems based on a niche model, *Journal of Wildlife and biodiversity*, 7(X), X-X. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7317180>

Abstract

Anthropogenic activities have caused habitat fragmentation and loss, which are the main threats to primates. Because of this, ecological niche models have become a widely used tool to determine the potential habitat of species. These models rarely include biotic factors, although vegetation variables such as height and phenology, data derived from remote sensing, were integrated into this research. We developed a model to obtain the potential distribution of the primate *A. palliata*. Therefore, records of the presence of monkeys in the field were collected, and later data were obtained on the spectral index of vegetation and the height of the canopy, derived from remote sensing, bioclimatic variables were also used. Subsequently, these variables were analyzed using the Variance Inflation Factor to discriminate those with the highest correlation. Finally, we use a Maximum Entropy algorithm included in the Maxent software, together with the presence registration data, vegetation index, height, and bioclimatic data. The predicted distribution of *A. palliata* was strongly associated with canopy height, vegetation index (RVI), and warmest quarter precipitation (Bio18). The areas with the highest probability of the presence of *A. palliata* are strongly associated with cocoa agrosystems and certain spaces of natural vegetation such as mangroves. With the integration of the variables derived from remote sensing, the potential distribution model obtained an excellent evaluation, to predict cocoa agrosystems as available habitats of the howler monkey *A. palliata*, thus identifying areas with a high probability of the presence of this species of primate, and thus offer a tool to decision-makers, to plan future studies and then establish criteria for the creation of areas for the conservation of primates in Mexico.

Keywords: Canopy height, Maxent, Remote sensing, Vegetation index

Introduction

The genus *Alouatta* is composed of at least 11 species, it is the genus with the greatest distribution in the American continent, from Mexico to Brazil and Argentina (Holzmann *et al.*, 2015). One of the characteristics that define this genus is that they live in arboreal environments with very high canopies, and their ability to include a large number of young leaves (sprouts) and flowers in their diet, in addition to adapting to small fragments of habitats (Chaves & Bicca-Marques, 2017). Of the two species of the genus *Alouatta* that inhabit Mexico, the howler monkey (*A. palliata*) has the largest distribution range in the country and the American continent (Rylands *et al.*, 2006).

In Mexico, this species has a potential distribution restricted to the states of Tabasco, Campeche, Quintana Roo, Yucatán, Veracruz, Oaxaca, and Chiapas (Cuarón *et al.*, 2008). However, land use change and deforestation have significantly reduced the original distribution of these primates (Estrada, 2015). Due to these changes in their original habitats, this species is adapting to exploit small fragments of habitats such as coffee and cocoa agrosystems (Arroyo-Rodríguez & Días, 2010), such is the case of Tabasco. Therefore, agrosystems, such as cocoa, have the potential to be habitats for wildlife and can be a very good alternative for native fauna (Alkorta *et al.*, 2003).

In Tabasco, Mexico, particularly in the municipality of Comalcalco, the howler monkey is known to have occupied anthropogenic environments such as cocoa agrosystems (Muñoz *et al.*, 2006; Estrada *et al.*, 2006), systems that replaced the original vegetation (Sánchez-Munguía, 2005), and with it, the natural habitat of the monkeys. This species uses the trees that provide shade to cocoa plantations, mostly large native trees (Muñoz *et al.*, 2006). There are investigations where the potential of these agrosystems as a habitat for monkeys has been studied, in terms of the best environmental and vegetation conditions, for their distribution in the area they occupy in agrosystems in the municipality of Comalcalco.

In terms of anthropogenic impacts, habitat fragmentation and loss are the main threats to primates (Pyritz *et al.*, 2010). Therefore, understanding the type of vegetation and the use of the tree stratum in primates is important to describe their pattern of habitat use (Li, 2007). The distribution of howler monkeys is strongly influenced by climatic and environmental factors, such as temperature, phenology, and vegetation height. Even more so, in cocoa agrosystems, since being an anthropogenic environment it has particular characteristics in its vegetation, mainly in the trees used as shade in the plantations, and in the case of howler monkeys, they have needed to use as available habitat (Muñoz *et al.*, 2006).

Ecological niche models have been widely used to determine the potential habitat of species. These models are based on the habitat characteristics (environmental variables) associated with the presence records of the target species, to define areas with similar or identical environmental conditions where the species may be present, and generate a map that represents the potential distribution of the species. The species (Calixto-Pérez *et al.*, 2018). Most ecological niche models only consider abiotic factors, such as climate and topography. Currently, work is being done with vegetation index, derived from remote sensing, to integrate them into an ecological niche model. MAXENT is an ecological niche modeling software that can predict the geographic distribution of species when only occurrence data are available for analysis (Phillips & Dudík, 2008).

Therefore, in the present study, our first objective was to delimit the potential distribution area of *A. palliata* in Comalcalco, Tabasco, Mexico to describe the environmental conditions that favor high suitability for the species in cacao agrosystems in the region.

Materials and methods

Study area

The municipality of Comalcalco is located at North latitude 18°16'57" and West longitude 93°13'30. It borders to the north with the municipality of Paraíso, to the south with the municipalities of Cunduacán and Jalpa de Méndez, to the east with Jalpa de Méndez and to the west with Cárdenas (Fig. 1). The average annual temperature of 27.1°C and an average annual rainfall of 1,926.1 mm (INEGI, 2017). The original vegetation was composed of medium evergreen forest (Palma-López *et al.*, 2007); Currently, cattle pastures and agricultural vegetation predominate (Ramos-Reyes *et al.*, 2016).

Figure 1. Map of the study area

Collection and processing of presence data

The records were obtained through

field data through direct observation, surveys, and interviews. The records obtained in the field were refined to avoid spatial correlation of the data and reduce sampling bias; since they are not eliminated, the model would tend to be underestimated (Luoto *et al.*, 2005, Peterson *et al.*, 2011; Halvorsen *et al.*, 2016). For this, the records were systematically selected in a subsample distributed in geographic space (Merckx *et al.*, 2011; Fourcade *et al.*, 2014). They were first projected as geo-referenced points in ArcGis 9.3, then a grid with 100 x 100 m quadrants was built throughout the study area using Hawth's Analysis tool. In each grid quadrant, a record was selected, eliminating those with more than one point per quadrant (Boria *et al.*, 2014; Fourcade *et al.*, 2014).

Pre-processing of satellite images

Sentinel satellite images were used, which were obtained from the portal: <https://scihub.copernicus.eu/dhus/#/home>. To which the geometric and radiometric correction was

applied through the ArcGIS v 9.2 software and the atmospheric correction through the QGIS v 2.18.10 software.

Vegetation Spectral Index

Nine vegetation indexes were calculated: Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), Ratio Vegetation Index (RVI), Soil-Adjusted Vegetation Index (SAVI), Enhanced Vegetation Index (EVI), Second Modified Soil Adjusted Vegetation Index (MSAVI2), Transformed Vegetation Index (TVI), Perpendicular Vegetation Index (PVI), Modified Soil Adjusted Vegetation Index (MSAVI1) and Ashburn Vegetation Index (AVI). The index was selected based on literature reports that associate them with the characterization of the vegetation.

Canopy height of shade trees

Height data were obtained by interpolating the Canopy Height Model (CHM) throughout the study area, using different extensions of the ArcGis v 9.2 software.

Bio-climatic variables

17 bioclimatic variables were analyzed, related to temperature and precipitation data in raster format (Ordoñez-Sierra, 2014) (Table 1).

Table 1. Description of the bioclimatic variables

Variable	Description of the variable
Bio1	Average annual temperature (°C)
Bio4	Temperature seasonality (standard deviation * 100)
Bio5	Maximum temperature of the warmest month (°C)
Bio6	Minimum temperature of the coldest month (°C)
Bio7	Annual temperature range (°C)(Bio5Bio6)
Bio8	Average temperature of the rainiest quarter (°C)
Bio9	Average temperature of the driest quarter (°C)
Bio10	Average temperature of the warmest quarter (°C)
Bio11	Average temperature of the coldest quarter (°C)

Bio12	Annual rainfall (mm)
Bio13	Precipitation of the wettest month (mm)
Bio14	Precipitation of the driest month (mm)
Bio15	Precipitation seasonality (coefficient of variation)
Bio16	Precipitation of the wettest quarter (mm)
Bio17	Precipitation of the driest quarter (mm)
Bio18	Precipitation of the warmest quarter (mm)
Bio19	Precipitation of the coldest quarter (mm)

Variance Inflation Factor (VIF)

The VIF was calculated of bioclimatic variables and spectral indices. To analyze the multicollinearity between variables. These analysis results can help to avoid the over-fitting phenomenon of the model.

Potential distribution modeling

To carry out the potential distribution model, the MAXENT program was used based on an ecological niche for the howler monkey (*A. palliata*) in cocoa agrosystems. MAXENT is based on a maximum entropy algorithm, spreading probabilities as uniformly as possible, subject to the constraints of observed values (ie known occurrences).

Model evaluation

To evaluate the performance of the final model, the ROC analysis within MAXENT will be used, and thus, obtain the values of the area under the AUC curve (Phillips *et al.*, 2006; Phillips & Dudik, 2008). To evaluate the performance of the model, what was established by Sweets (1988) was considered: AUC 1-0.9 = excellent; 0.9-0.8 = good; 0.8-0.7 = acceptable; 0.7-0.6 = poor; 0.6-0.5 = not suitable. This analysis provides sensitivity and specificity values, the average percentage contribution of each variable to the model, and the analysis of the contribution of each variable to the model (Phillips *et al.*, 2006). The MAXENT analysis was run using 75% of the records as training data to build the model and the remaining 25% to test the model. This approach is conservative in estimating ecological niches since it eliminates extreme values that can result from misidentifications or georeferencing.

Results

Presence data collection

A total of 65 records of the presence of howler monkeys (*A. palliata*) in cocoa agrosystems were obtained.

Multicollinearity between variables

The bioclimatic variables and vegetation index least collinearity were: RVI, Bio18, and Height (Fig. 2). Therefore, for the potential distribution model, the variable Precipitation of the Warmest Quarter (Bio18), Ratio Vegetation Index (RVI) and Vegetation Height (Altura) was used, since they were the variables that contributed the most in a model applied in cocoa agrosystems, to predict the presence of the howler monkey (*A. palliata*).

variable	altura	bio1	bio4	bio5	bio6	bio7	bio10	bio11	bio12	bio13	bio14	bio15	bio16	bio17	bio18	bio19	avi	evi	msav1	msav2	ndi	pi	rvi	savi	tv
altura	0.756	1.075	0.749	0.817	1.113	0.845	0.779	0.869	0.849	0.911	1.048	0.845	0.917	0.904	0.876	1.512	1.550	1.580	1.575	1.605	1.513	0.760	1.567	1.551	
bio1		0.865	4.744	2.018	0.822	2.747	4.028	1.000	1.006	0.950	0.999	1.022	0.984	0.937	1.154	0.768	0.769	0.765	0.765	0.787	0.767	1.324	0.766	0.792	
bio4			1.496	0.533	51.89	2.495	0.575	0.774	22.13	1.209	0.771	26.34	1.167	0.960	0.579	0.970	0.953	1.204	0.967	0.933	0.971	1.091	0.961	0.929	
bio5				1.157	1.285	4.448	1.590	1.263	1.091	1.578	0.724	1.183	1.572	1.338	0.851	0.822	0.813	0.932	0.810	0.795	0.821	1.288	0.809	0.803	
bio6					0.517	0.764	18.15	2.013	19.59	1.118	1.018	2.707	1.162	1.386	2.598	0.983	0.995	7.362	0.976	0.994	0.981	0.973	0.982	1.007	
bio7						2.380	0.556	0.704	0.540	1.027	0.867	0.639	0.992	0.844	0.600	0.944	0.929	9.844	0.944	0.921	0.944	1.119	0.938	0.914	
bio10							0.988	0.698	6.610	0.871	1.048	0.678	0.858	0.748	0.777	0.749	0.743	8.959	0.749	0.761	0.749	1.454	0.745	0.760	
bio11								1.575	28.43	1.038	1.030	1.879	1.087	1.202	2.114	0.887	0.895	9.066	0.882	0.904	0.886	1.078	0.886	0.915	
bio12									1.533	7.748	0.580	0.688	8.223	0.601	1.101	1.371	1.355	1.312	1.319	1.177	1.369	0.838	1.332	1.203	
bio13										0.979	1.384	2.303	0.927	0.886	10.90	0.971	0.978	0.965	0.966	0.962	0.970	1.015	0.966	0.971	
bio14											0.520	3.832	84.39	2.521	0.778	1.396	1.362	1.330	1.337	1.154	1.395	0.855	1.346	1.174	
bio15												0.655	0.513	0.610	1.775	0.778	0.789	0.798	0.796	0.871	0.779	1.218	0.792	0.861	
bio16													3.710	0.722	1.464	1.279	1.271	1.233	1.238	1.133	1.277	0.861	1.248	1.157	
bio17														1.848	0.755	1.414	1.381	1.348	1.355	1.177	1.413	0.843	1.366	1.198	
bio18															0.833	1.427	1.401	1.362	1.370	0.968	1.425	0.828	1.383	1.228	
bio19																0.908	0.918	0.910	0.910	0.809	7.240	1.064	12.06	87.72	
avi																	102.49	105.708	79.217	0.974	105.31	0.553	107.31	6.546	
evi																		101.332	100.577	0.946	86.84	0.543	101.57	8.452	
msav1																			108.401	0.750	100.18	0.548	80.63	7.626	
msav2																				0.881	80.78	0.547	100.91	7.732	
ndi																					0.907	0.506	0.91	0.936	
pi																						0.555	101.39	6.407	
rvi																							0.536	0.502	
savi																								10.236	
tv																									

Figure 2. Table showing values of Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) of bioclimatic variables and vegetation index. Values of more than 10 are indicated in red and bold.

Potential distribution modeling

Areas with a potential distribution of *A. palliata* are shown in red, gradually decreasing to low probability in blue (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Potential distribution of *A. palliata* in cocoa agrosystems

Model evaluation

The MAXENT model for *A. palliata* achieved an excellent score with mean ROC curve values having an AUC of 0.935 for training data and 0.940 for test data, and a minimal presence of training of 0.095 (Fig. 4).

Figure 4. ROC curve derived from the potential distribution model of *A. palliata*

In the Jackknife test, height was the variable with the highest gain when it was run in isolation, and since it was not included in the model, the gain decreased, so it seems to have the greatest amount of useful information for the model than the other variables (Fig. 5).

Figure 5. Jackknife test of the distribution model for *A. palliata*

Discussion

The main difference between niche and distribution models is that distribution models are a cartographic representation of the suitability of space for the presence of a species based on the variables used to generate said representation (Maciel-Mata *et al.*, 2015; Mateo *et al.*, 2011). While the ecological niche model is the combination of ecological conditions in which a species can survive and reproduce (Maciel-Mata *et al.*, 2015; Pablos *et al.*, 2010). The concept of niche is central to ecology. It is widely used to describe both the range of conditions necessary for the persistence of the species and its ecological role in the ecosystem (Polechová & Storch, 2008), and variables such as structure and phenology can be integrated through ecological niche models of vegetation.

In this study, the potential distribution model was developed with the MaxEnt software, to describe the probability of the distribution of *A. palliata* in cocoa agrosystems, using vegetation characteristics as in other niche models. For example, to analyze the vertical structure of certain reptile communities, data derived from LiDAR (Sillero & Goncalves-Seco, 2014) and spectral index such as NDVI were used to estimate the distribution of *Bithynia siamensis goniomphalos* (Pratumchart *et al.*, 2019), these models used data derived from remote sensing. However, previous models to predict available habitats for howler monkeys (*A. palliata*) have only used bioclimatic data, (Calixto-Pérez *et al.*, 2018), and no vegetation features are associated with the presence of these primates. In this sense, the data derived from remote sensing, particularly LiDAR, are opening up new knowledge in the ecology of species (Sillero *et al.*, 2009; Sillero *et al.*, 2012).

This potential distribution model was generated using data derived from remote sensing, so to determine the importance of the variables, the Jackknife test was applied, through which it was determined that the main variables related to the potential distribution of *A. palliata* in cocoa agrosystems, in order of importance were: the height of the vegetation obtained through LiDAR technology, the spectral vegetation index RVI and the bioclimatic variable bio18. However, there are previous studies of niche models for primates, although not in cocoa agrosystems and using only bioclimatic variables, where the variables with the highest gain were: bio5 for *Alouatta pigra*, bio19 for *A. palliata* and bio9 for *Ateles geoffroyi*. Therefore, the variables that both models have detected as important are obtained using new habitat mapping tools, such as LiDAR; this provides an improvement in the reliability of habitat mapping in anthropogenic landscapes as a case study (Valle *et al.*, 2011).

To evaluate the predictive accuracy of the model, the ROC curve was used, in which the AUC values of training and testing of the model were excellent at 0.93 and 0.94, respectively. All these results can be used to define favorable areas for monkeys and implement conservation programs (Barbosa *et al.*, 2003).

The Maxent model indicated cocoa agrosystems and mangroves for *A. palliata* as available habitats. In other countries, there are mangrove-dwelling monkeys, such as the proboscis monkey (*Nasalis larvatus*), an endangered primate endemic to the island of Borneo in Indonesia, which inhabits mangroves, peatlands, and riparian forests (Bernard *et al.*, 2011). Capuchin monkeys (*Sapajus flavius* and *Cebus capucinus*), occupy the mangroves in Malaysia, for rest, shelter, and food (Medeiros *et al.*, 2019), which demonstrates the adaptability of these animals. These species, like many, are affected by the loss of their habitat, due to both human activities and natural disasters (Harding, 2015). The importance of mangroves in the study area is due to the trend in changing land use, of cocoa agrosystems. Therefore, the behavioral adaptability of these monkeys and their ability to exploit a variety of food sources have played a key role in their survival, since despite being considered arboreal, they also use the ground to search for vegetables, invertebrates, and small vertebrates as food (Medeiros *et al.*, 2019).

Niche models can describe demographic, birth, and death rates of individuals, and this translate into population dynamics, for species threatened by local extinction (Schurr *et al.*, 2012), this type of model can measure the degree of spatial connectivity between populations based on environmental suitability (Soley-Guardia *et al.*, 2016). Some studies describe habitat connectivity as having important effects on metapopulation dynamics since it determines regional persistence and the genetic diversity of species in fragmented landscapes (San Vicente & Valencia, 2012; Schooley & Branch, 2011). ; Mühlner *et al.*, 2010), as could be the case of howler monkeys in cocoa agrosystems. However, few studies in Mexico have addressed the conservation of the primate population from a metapopulation perspective, such as the one carried out by Escobedo-Morales & Mandujano (2007) for *A. palliata*, in Los Tuxtlas, Mexico, where those populations Occupying patch-like habitats, connected by establishing corridors of vegetation, significantly enhance metapopulation persistence.

Conclusion

Spatial modeling based on data derived from remote sensing, to obtain certain vegetation characteristics such as height and phenology, is considered a powerful tool, mainly through the use of new technologies such as LiDAR for mapping the structure of the habitat of the species. With the integration of these types of variables, in the present study, the potential distribution was estimated, and an excellent evaluation was obtained, to predict the available habitats of the howler monkey *A. palliata* in cocoa agrosystems, since the integration of the three variables height, vegetation index and bioclimatic, turned out to be an acceptable approach. Although the study was carried out in cocoa agrosystems, information on suitability was also obtained on certain spaces of natural vegetation such as mangroves, these spaces could be of great ecological importance for howler monkeys due to their behavioral adaptability since in other countries certain species of tree monkeys have used them as a refuge. Therefore, this type of potential distribution model is an important tool for decision-makers in the evaluation of certain valuable spaces for the conservation of species threatened by local extinction.

Acknowledgments

We appreciate the donations from the IdeaWild teams, for the development of this research for the conservation of biodiversity. The first author acknowledges support from the Mexican Consejo Nacional de Ciencia y Tecnología (CONACyT) through a scholarship to pursue graduate studies.

References

- Arroyo-Rodríguez, V., y Dias, P. A. D. (2010). Effects of habitat fragmentation and disturbance on howler monkeys: a review. *American Journal of Primatology*, 72(1), 1-16. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ajp.20753>
- Alkorta, I., Albizu, I., y Garbisu, C. (2003). Biodiversity and agroecosystems. *Biodiversity and conservation*, 12(12), 2521-2522.
- Barbosa, A. M., Real, R., Olivero, J., y Vargas, J. M. (2003). Otter (*Lutra lutra*) distribution modeling at two resolution scales suited to conservation planning in the Iberian Peninsula. *Biological conservation*, 114(3), 377-387. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0006-3207\(03\)00066-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0006-3207(03)00066-1)
- Bernard, H., Matsuda, I., Hanya, G., & Ahmad, A. H. (2011). Characteristics of night sleeping trees of proboscis monkeys (*Nasalis larvatus*) in Sabah, Malaysia. *International Journal of Primatology*, 32(1), 259-267.
- Boria, R. A., Olson, L. E., Goodman, S. M., y Anderson, R. P. (2014). Spatial filtering to reduce sampling bias can improve the performance of ecological niche models. *Ecological Modelling*, 275, 73-77. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolmodel.2013.12.012>

- Calixto-Pérez, E., Alarcón-Guerrero, J., Ramos-Fernández, G., Dias, P. A. D., Rangel-Negrín, A., Améndola-Pimenta, M., & Urquiza-Haas, T. (2018). Integrating expert knowledge and ecological niche models to estimate Mexican primates' distribution. *Primates*, 59(5), 451-467. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10329-018-0673-8>
- Chaves, Ó. M., y Bicca-Marques, J. C. (2017). Crop feeding by brown howlers (*Alouatta guariba clamitans*) in forest fragments: The conservation value of cultivated species. *International Journal of Primatology*, 38(2), 263-281.
- Cuarón, A.D., Shedden, A., Rodríguez-Luna, E., de Grammont, P.C., Link, A., Palacios, E., Morales, A. y Cortés-Ortiz, L. (2008). *Alouatta palliata*. The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species 2008: e.T39960A10280447.
- Escobedo-Morales, L. A., & Mandujano, S. (2007). Conservación del mono aullador en la reserva de la biosfera Los Tuxtlas, Veracruz: un enfoque metapoblacional. *Hacia una cultura de conservación de la diversidad biológica*, 131-140.
- Estrada, A. (2015). Conservation of *Alouatta*: Social and economic drivers of habitat loss, information vacuum, and mitigating population declines. In *Howler monkeys* (pp. 383-409). Springer, New York, NY.
- Estrada, A., Saenz, J., Harvey, C., Naranjo, E., Muñoz, D., y Rosales-Meda, M. (2006). Primates in agroecosystems: conservation value of some agricultural practices in Mesoamerican landscapes. In *New Perspectives in the Study of Mesoamerican Primates* (pp. 437-470). Springer US.
- Elith, J., Graham, C. H., Anderson, R. P., Dudík, M., Ferrier, S., Guisan, A., Hijmans, R. J., Huettmann, F., Leathwick, R., Lehmann, A., Li, J., Lohmann L. G., Loiselle, B. A., Manion, G., Moritz, C., Nakamura, M., akazawa, Y., Overton, J. M., Peterson, A. T., Phillips, S. J., Richardson, K., Scachetti-Pereira, R., Schapire, R. E., Soberón, J., Williams, S., Wisz, M. S., y Zimmermann N. E. (2006). Novel methods improve prediction of species' distributions from occurrence data. *Ecography*, 129-151. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.2006.0906-7590.04596.x>
- Fourcade, Y., Engler, J. O., Rödder, D., y Secondi, J. (2014). Mapping species distributions with MAXENT using a geographically biased sample of presence data: a performance assessment of methods for correcting sampling bias. *PloS one*, 9(5), e97122. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0097122>
- Harding, L. E. (2015). *Nasalis larvatus* (Primates: Colobini). *Mammalian Species*, 47(926), 84-99. <https://doi.org/10.1093/mspecies/sev009>
- Holzmann, I., Agostini, I., DeMatteo, K., Areta, J. I., Merino, M. L., y Di Bitetti, M. S. (2015). Using species distribution modeling to assess factors that determine the distribution of two parapatric Howlers (*Alouatta* spp.) in South America. *International Journal of Primatology*, 36(1), 18-32. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10764-014-9805-1>
- Halvorsen, R., Mazzoni, S., Dirksen, J. W., Næsset, E., Gobakken, T., y Ohlson, M. (2016). How important are choice of model selection method and spatial autocorrelation of presence data

- for distribution modelling by MaxEnt? *Ecological modelling*, 328, 108-118. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolmodel.2016.02.021>
- INEGI (2017). Anuario estadístico y geográfico de Tabasco 2017. Instituto Nacional de Estadística y Geografía. Gobierno de la República Mexicana.
- Li, Y. (2007). Terrestriality and tree stratum use in a group of Sichuan snub-nosed monkeys. *Primates*, 48(3), 197-207.
- Luoto, M., Pöyry, J., Heikkinen, R. K., y Saarinen, K. (2005). Uncertainty of bioclimate envelope models based on the geographical distribution of species. *Global Ecology and biogeography*, 14(6), 575-584. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1466-822X.2005.00186.x>
- Maciel-Mata, C. A., Manríquez-Morán, N., Octavio-Aguilar, P., & Sánchez-Rojas, G. (2015). El área de distribución de las especies: revisión del concepto. *Acta universitaria*, 25(2), 03-19.
- Mateo, R. G., Felicísimo, Á. M., y Muñoz, J. (2011). Modelos de distribución de especies: Una revisión sintética. *Revista chilena de historia natural*, 84(2), 217-240. <http://dx.doi.org/10.4067/S0716-078X2011000200008>
- Merckx, B., Steyaert, M., Vanreusel, A., Vincx, M., y Vanaverbeke, J. (2011). Null models reveal preferential sampling, spatial autocorrelation and overfitting in habitat suitability modelling. *Ecological Modelling*, 222(3), 588-597. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolmodel.2010.11.016>
- Medeiros, K., Bastos, M., Jones, G., & Bezerra, B. (2019). Behavior, Diet, and Habitat Use by Blonde Capuchin Monkeys (*Sapajus flavius*) in a Coastal Area Prone to Flooding: Direct Observations and Camera Trapping. *International Journal of Primatology*, 40(4-5), 511-531.
- Muñoz, D., Estrada, A., Naranjo, E., & Ochoa, S. (2006). Foraging ecology of howler monkeys in a cacao (*Theobroma cacao*) plantation in Comalcalco, Mexico. *American Journal of Primatology: Official Journal of the American Society of Primatologists*, 68(2), 127-142. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ajp.20211>
- Mühlner, S., Kormann, U., Schmidt-Entling, M., Herzog, F., & Bailey, D. (2010). Structural versus functional habitat connectivity measures to explain bird diversity in fragmented orchards. *Journal of Landscape Ecology*, 3(1), 52-64.
- Ordoñez Sierra R. (2014). Modelado espacio-temporal de desfase y amplitud de la variabilidad climática en la cuenca Lerma-Chapala-Santiago. Tesis de Maestría. Centro Interamericano de Recursos del Agua, Facultad de Ingeniería, Universidad Autónoma del Estado de México. Toluca, Estado de México. 155 p. <http://hdl.handle.net/20.500.11799/109524>
- Pablos, N. S., Barbosa, A. M., Freiría, F. M., & Real, R. (2010). Los modelos de nicho ecológico en la herpetología ibérica: pasado, presente y futuro. *Boletín de la Asociación Herpetológica Española*, (21), 2-24.
- Palma-López, D. J., Cisneros, D. J., Moreno, C. E., y Rincón-Ramírez, J. A. (2007). Suelos de Tabasco: su uso y manejo sustentable. Colegio de Postgraduados-ISPROTAB-FUPROTAB. Villahermosa, Tabasco, México. 195 pp.
- Pratumchart, K., Suwannatrai, K., Sereewong, C., Thinkhamrop, K., Chaiyos, J., Boonmars, T., & Suwannatrai, A. T. (2019). Ecological Niche Model based on Maximum Entropy for mapping distribution of *Bithynia siamensis goniomphalos*, first intermediate host snail of

- Opisthorchis viverrini in Thailand. *Acta tropica*, 193, 183-191. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actatropica.2019.03.004>
- Peterson, A. T., & Soberón, J. (2012). Species distribution modeling and ecological niche modeling: getting the concepts right. *Natureza & Conservação*, 10(2), 102-107.
- Phillips, S. J., y Dudík, M. (2008). Modeling of species distributions with Maxent: new extensions and a comprehensive evaluation. *Ecography*, 31(2), 161-175. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.0906-7590.2008.5203.x>
- Peterson A. T., Soberón J., Pearson R. G., Anderson R. P., Martínez-Meyer E., Nakamura M., Bastos-Araújo M. (2011) *Ecological Niches and Geographic Distributions*. Princeton University Press. Consulted: 20/May/2017.
- Phillips, S. J., Anderson, R. P., y Schapire, R. E. (2006). Maximum entropy modeling of species geographic distributions. *Ecological modelling*, 190(3-4), 231-259. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolmodel.2005.03.026>
- Polechová, J., & Storch, D. (2008). Ecological niche. *Encyclopedia of ecology*, 2, 1088-1097.
- Pyritz, L. W., Büntge, A. B., Herzog, S. K., & Kessler, M. (2010). Effects of habitat structure and fragmentation on diversity and abundance of primates in tropical deciduous forests in Bolivia. *International journal of primatology*, 31(5), 796-812.
- Ramos-Reyes, R., Sánchez-Hernández, R., y Gama-Campillo, L. M. (2016). Análisis de cambios de uso del suelo en el municipio costero de Comalcalco, Tabasco, México. *Ecosistemas y recursos agropecuarios*, 3(8), 151-160.
- Rylands, A. B., Groves, C. P., Mittermeier, R. A., Cortés-Ortiz, L., y Hines, J. J. (2006). Taxonomy and distributions of Mesoamerican primates. In *New perspectives in the study of Mesoamerican primates* (pp. 29-79). Springer, Boston, MA. https://doi.org/10.1007/0-387-25872-8_3
- Sánchez-Munguía, A. (2005). *Uso del suelo agropecuario y deforestación en Tabasco 1950-2000*. Universidad Juárez Autónoma de Tabasco. 123 pp.
- San Vicente, M. G., & Valencia, P. J. L. (2012). Efectos de la fragmentación de hábitats y pérdida de conectividad ecológica dentro de la dinámica territorial. *Polígonos. Revista de geografía*, (16), 35-54. <http://dx.doi.org/10.18002/pol.v0i16.410>
- Sillero, N., & Goncalves-Seco, L. (2014). Spatial structure analysis of a reptile community with airborne LiDAR data. *International Journal of Geographical Information Science*, 28(8), 1709-1722. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/13658816.2014.902062>
- Sillero, N., Brito, J. C., Skidmore, A. K., & Toxopeus, A. G. (2009). Biogeographical patterns derived from remote sensing variables: the amphibians and reptiles of the Iberian Peninsula. *Amphibia-Reptilia*, 30(2), 185-206.
- Sillero, N., Brito, J., Martín-Alfageme, S., García-Meléndez, E., Toxopeus, A., & Skidmore, A. (2012). The significance of using satellite imagery data only in Ecological Niche Modelling of Iberian herps. *Acta herpetologica*, 7(2), 221-237.
- Schurr, F. M., Pagel, J., Cabral, J. S., Groeneveld, J., Bykova, O., O'Hara, R. B., & Schröder, B. (2012). How to understand species' niches and range dynamics: a demographic research

agenda for biogeography. *Journal of Biogeography*, 39(12), 2146-2162.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2699.2012.02737.x>

Schooley, R. L., & Branch, L. C. (2011). Habitat quality of source patches and connectivity in fragmented landscapes. *Biodiversity and Conservation*, 20(8), 1611-1623.

Soley-Guardia, M., Gutiérrez, E. E., Thomas, D. M., Ochoa-G, J., Aguilera, M., & Anderson, R. P. (2016). Are we overestimating the niche? Removing marginal localities helps ecological niche models detect environmental barriers. *Ecology and evolution*, 6(5), 1267-1279.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/ece3.1900>

Sweets, J. A. 1988. Measuring the accuracy of diagnostic systems. *Science* 240: 1285-1293. DOI: 10.1126/science.3287615

Title P.O., y Bemmels J.B. (2018). ENVIREM: an expanded set of bioclimatic and topographic variables increases flexibility and improves performance of ecological niche modeling. *Ecography*. 41:291–307. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ecog.02880>

Valle, M., Borja, Á., Chust, G., Galparsoro, I., & Garmendia, J. M. (2011). Modelling suitable estuarine habitats for *Zostera noltii*, using ecological niche factor analysis and bathymetric LiDAR. *Estuarine, Coastal and Shelf Science*, 94(2), 144-154.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecss.2011.05.031>